

4C'S IN TEACHING THROUGH PROBLEM SOLVING (TTP) IN GRADE 7- MATHEMATICS

**AGNES F. ARELLANO¹, CLEIANN R. MALIGO², GERLIE D. MAMBA³,
RESTIE Q. MASALUNGA⁴**

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3853-3649>¹, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2022-8339>²,

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0760-2050>³, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4110-1257>⁴

agnes.arellan@g.batstate-u.edu.ph¹, cleiann.maligo@g.batstate-u.edu.ph²,

gerlie.mamba@g.batstate-u.edu.ph³, restie.masalunga@g.batstate-u.edu.ph⁴

Batangas State University

Pablo Borbon, Rizal Avenue, Batangas City, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Today, mathematics education faces the critical challenge of strengthening its goal of cultivating problem solvers and critical thinkers. Owing to that, it becomes a challenge for teachers to utilized problem-solving instruction in their educational setting. Mathematics teachers are much aware on how important problem-solving in enhancing the learning skills of the students. This study focused on problem-solving instruction, also known as teaching through problem solving (TTP), as an academic intervention in teaching mathematics and examined its extent of utilization and development of student's competencies relative to 4C's. This quantitative-descriptive research focused in 4Cs in TTP in Grade 7- Mathematics of Batangas City Division. This study utilized a survey questionnaire as its primary tool in data gathering. The researcher's target respondents were the 109 Grade 7-10 teachers rendering their teaching service at Batangas City Division. The frequency and weighted mean were the statistical tools used for the treatment of the gathered data. The study's findings showed that TTP could be incorporated into various Grade - 7 Mathematics lessons. Teachers were capable enough to adopt multiple approaches and implement various instructional methods to equip learners with the skill and knowledge to assist them throughout their lives. Moreover, the utilization of TTP as a teaching method plays a significant role in developing the learning skills (4Cs) of students in learning Grade – 7 mathematics. The study proposed problem-solving-based activities about 11 mathematics lessons and intendedly designed under TTP.

Keywords: teaching through problem solving, 4C's skills, Grade 7- Mathematics, development of students' competencies, quantitative-descriptive research, Philippines